

April 30, 2023

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Assessment of Crop Rading by Wild Animals in Ayetoro, Ogun State

Author's Details:

¹Odebiyi, B. R., ²Odunlami, S. S., ³Oyeleye, D. O., ¹Adewale, R. O. ¹Oso, A. O. and ¹Banjo, O. B.

⁽¹⁾Department of Forestry, Wildlife and Fisheries, College of Agricultural Sciences, Olabisi Onabanjo University P.M.B. 0012, Ayetoro, Ogun State, Nigeria ⁽²⁾Department of Forestry and Wildlife Management, University of Port Harcourt, Rivers state, Nigeria. ⁽³⁾Department of Forestry Technology, Federal College of Forestry, Jos, Plateau state, Nigeria. *Corresponding author's email address: jideodebiyi@ouagoiwoye.edu.ng

Received Date: 04-Feb-2023

Accepted Date: 14-Mar-2023

Published Date: 30-Apr-2023

Abstract

Crop raiding is undoubtedly the most reported case of human-wildlife conflict. Crop raiding is not a new phenomenon. Since the pre-colonial era, elephants and other large mammals have been implicated in some parts of Africa to be responsible for food shortage, displacement of rural dwellers and preventing the cultivation of crops. Human wildlife conflicts have however gained more global attention in the past few decades among stakeholders. These conflicts now have far reaching implications on conservation efforts, livelihoods, food security and even national security. Strategies to resolve these conflicts should be site specific. We therefore assessed the crop raiding activities of wild animals in Ayetoro, Ogun state, Nigeria, with a view to providing the much needed information required for conflict resolution. The sampling technique deployed was focus group discussion. Farmers were drawn from farming communities to discuss issues relating to crop raiding by wild animals on their farms. Data elicited from the discussion were subjected to content analysis. Four themes emerged from the study; maize (*Zea mays*) and cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) were the most raided crops, the most frequently reported crop raiding wild animal was grasscutter (*Thryonomys swinderianus*), wild animals raided the farmers' crops in both wet and dry season but was more in intense in the wet season while the method adopted by the farmers in preventing crop loss were guarding and regular weeding of their farms and surroundings. Crop damage mitigation measures should have a holistic approach in order to yield the desired results. There is an urgent need for government intervention in order to cushion the effect of the loss incurred by the farmers.

Keywords: Crop raiding, Human-wildlife conflict, Ayetoro, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Crop raiding is undoubtedly the most reported case of human-wildlife conflict. With the exception of wild animals' attack on humans, crop raiding stands out among other causes of conflict between man and wild animals; such as livestock depredation by wild animals, spread of diseases to livestock, destruction of farm infrastructure e.tc. (Kate, 2012, Anand and Radhakris). (Woodroffe *et al.*, 2005) described crop raiding as the most wide spread and serious conflicts between man and wild animals. Crop raiding is the movement of wild animals from their natural habitat into farm lands to consume agricultural produce cultivated by man (Sillero-Zubiri and Switzer 2001). The main issues about crop raiding is wild animals feasting on cultigens which mostly results in major crop damage or outright crop loss in extreme cases (Saj *et al.* 2001) For instance, 40%

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of all the crops cultivated in a farm in the Ruaha Ecosystem was destroyed by wild animals that invaded the farmland (Kabebele, 2011).

Crop raiding, just like other human-wildlife conflicts is not a new phenomenon. For back as the pre-colonial era, elephants and other large mammals have been implicated in some parts of Africa to be responsible for food shortage, displacement of rural dwellers and eventually preventing the cultivation of crops (Naughton-Treves, 1999). Human wildlife conflicts have however gained more global attention in the past few decades among stakeholders such as conservation biologists, government functionaries, ecologist, community leaders, geographers, conservation based non-governmental organizations, amongst others (Siljande *et al.*, 2020; Hoare, 2000; Osborn and Parker, 2003). The basis for the recent and growing global interest in human wildlife conflict is not far-fetched. These conflicts now have far reaching implications on conservation efforts, livelihoods, food security and even national security. According to Thirgood *et al.* (2005), wild animals could cause considerable loss of human lives and livelihood. Paying lip service to this menace would not be in the interest of wildlife conservation because it could result in the reprisal killing of wild animals and sharp decline in wild animal population. Financial loss incurred by famers because of wild animals raiding their farms can significantly impede conservation programmes due to animosity of the farmers towards the wild animals.

Reports of crop raiding by wild animals has sky rocketed in recent times for seemingly obvious reasons. There is a growing competition for space and natural resources between man and wildlife. Hill (1997) attributed rising human wildlife conflict to a spike in the rate at which virgin lands are being converted to farmlands. Several natural habitats of wild animals and natural landscapes have been modified into agricultural landscapes (Thirgood *et al.*, 2005).

In most of these conflicts, the subsistence rural farmers are often the worst hit. Crop raiding is a pertinent issue with severe and undesirable implications on the livelihoods of small holder farmers. Small holder farmers largely depend on the proceeds from their farms and as such, either slight or major crop damage can be really catastrophic. Consequently, local food security becomes a challenge (Siljande *et al.*, 2020).

FAO (2015) reported that over 33m people resident in African mountains and highlands are susceptible to food insecurity and a substantial number of these people are subsistence farmers who depend on rain fed agriculture for their survival. Small holder farmers bear the brunt of crop raiding more than any other stakeholder through the loss of food on the table and lack money in their pockets (Osborn and Parker, 2003; Marchal and Hill 2009). Elephants (*Loxodonta africana*) and some other large mammals have been found to be notorious in crop raiding. A variety of wild animals have been implicated by farmers in the destruction of their crops and farmlands. Human-wildlife conflict involving elephants and farmers are predominant in most African countries and constitute a major threat to elephant conservation. Elephants have destroyed not only farms but even attacked and killed several farmers. Sadly, this has caused resentment and animosity among the rural populace affected by this menace (Naughton-Treves *et al.*, 1999).

In an attempt to resolve these conflicts, it is paramount to state that the strategies to adopt should be site specific because the key issues and drivers of the conflict vary across regions. This necessitated the need to access the crop raiding activities of wild animals in rural communities in Ayetoro, Ogun State, Nigeria. Consolidating on the existing knowledge base of human-wildlife conflict, specifically farmers-wildlife conflict cannot be over emphasized because this will further provide the much needed information required for conflict resolution.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

The study was conducted in Ayetoro, Yewa North Local government area of Ogun state, Nigeria. Ayetoro lies on latitude 7° 12'N and longitude 30° 30'E in a deciduous derived savanna zone of Ogun state, although it is surrounded by a number of Forest reserves, including Ilaro and Imeko Forest reserves. It has a sub-humid tropical climate with an average annual rainfall of 1, 909.30mm. Ayetoro is made up of an undulating surface drained mainly by Rori and Ayinbo rivers. It is an agro-ecological zone that lies between 90 and 120m above sea level. The residents of the community are predominantly farmers noted for the cultivation of arable crops.

Data Collection

The sampling technique adopted was Focus group discussion. It is a research technique whereby a researcher coordinates a group of individuals with common identity to discuss a particular subject matter (Hayward *et al.*, 2004). In this case, farmers were drawn from farming communities to discuss issues of crop raiding by wild animals on their farms. The guidelines for the implementation of focus group discussion as provided by Morgan *et al.* (1998) were strictly adhered to.

The lead author played the role of a “moderator” during the group discussion. The group discussion was held at the farmers’ statutory meeting point of the farmers’ association. The choice of the venue was made based on ease of accessibility and location. The participants were expected to be comfortable, at ease and free from distractions, in line with Macfarlane Smith (1972) and the selected venue met these requirements. The group size was put at 12, as recommended by Fern (1982).

At the commencement of the discussion, the moderator gave an opening remark by introducing himself and stating the essence and scope of the discussion. The participants were equally given the privilege of introducing themselves. Data elicited during the discussion was subjected to content analysis as prescribed by Morgan *et al.*, (1998).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following themes emerged from our study; maize (*Zea mays*) and cassava (*Manihot esculenta*) were the most raided crops, the most frequently reported crop raiding wild animal was grasscutter (*Thryonomys swinderianus*), wild animals raided the farmers’ crops in both wet and dry season but the raid was more intense in the wet season while the method adopted by the farmers in preventing crop loss were guarding and regular weeding of their farms and surroundings.

Since time immemorial, maize has remained a staple crop cultivated by African farmers. It is also a delight and delicacy for several crop raiding wild animals. (Siljande *et al.* 2020) described maize together with cassava as the most attacked crops by wild animals. Similarly, Naughton-Treves (1997) rated cassava and maize among crops with the highest rate of vulnerability to crop raiding mammals. Our findings also corroborated that of Adebowale *et al.*, (2021) where maize and cassava were ranked among crop types severely damaged by wild animals in farms around Old Oyo National Park in Nigeria. Elsewhere in Banja Woreda, Awi Zone, Ethiopia, maize was ranked as crop with highest risk of destruction by wildlife crop raiders (Derebe *et al.*, 2022). A total of 912 damage took place on farmlands where maize and other cultigens were planted in Gera district, southwestern Ethiopia (Gobosho *et al.*, 2015). This pattern further concurs with the findings of (Odebiyi and Alarape, 2018) where maize was the crop mostly attacked by Olive baboons (*Papio anubis*).

Maize is a cereal crop cultivated widely across Africa in diverse agro-ecological environment. More maize is produced annually than any other grain. Maize grains are rich in vitamins A, C and E, carbohydrates and essential minerals and contains 9 % protein. It is also rich in dietary fibre and calories which is a good source of energy. This certainly explains why it has become a highly sought after crop by wild animals outside protected areas. Maize is the most important cereal crop in Sub-Sahara Africa (SSA) and an important staple food for more than 1.2 billion people in SSA and Latin America. Maize accounts for 30-50 % of low income household expenditures in Eastern and Southern Africa. It is also the preferred animal feed in many regions. Maize is processed and prepared in various forms depending on the country. It is prepared into porridge in Eastern and Southern Africa, while maize flour is made into porridge in West Africa. Ground maize is also fried or baked in many countries. In all parts of Africa, fresh maize is boiled or roasted on its cob and served as a snack. Popcorn is also a popular snack (International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, 2009). Maize is practically indispensable in local food diet (Hill 2000). Maize and most other mature crops offers nutritional reward to the raiding wild animals. This cultigen is usually delicious to the wild animals, with high calorie content and consequently reducing time spent in searching for food in the wild (Malugu and Hoare 2007; Ntalwila *et al.* 2011).

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Grasscutter (*Thryonomys Swinderianus*) being the most reported wildlife pest in the study area contradicted most other reports of farmer-wildlife conflicts. Often times, large mammals are referred to, as the most notorious crop raiders. For instance, Naughton-Treves *et al.*, (1998) elicited elephants, chimpanzees and bush pigs as being among the most important crop damaging wild animals around the hard edge of Kibale National Park, Uganda. They went further by submitting that, not only did the farmers incur direct cost but also bore indirect cost, such as movement restriction, disruption of sleep, haphazard school attendance and vulnerability to malaria arising from the need to guard their farmlands from elephants. In the same vein, out of 38 different wildlife pest reviewed by Naughton-Treves and Treves (2005), elephant was rated as the worst and most problematic animal.

However, on the contrary, smaller animals like grasscutter could impose greater cost and farmers suffer more loss when compared with the activities of larger mammals. Our findings were corroborated by (Mascarenhas, 1971; Gesicho, 1991; Hawkes, 1991; and Gillingham and Lee, 1999) who all attested to the fact that elephants and some large ungulates were unfairly held responsible for crop raiding and that smaller animals like rodents, for e.g. grasscutter, can in reality wreck more havoc, over time than the large mammals. As a matter of fact, elephants in Kibale were reported to have a relatively minimal economic implication when compared to the activities of rodents and other invertebrate pests on farm lands (Naughton-Treves and Treves, 2005).

We found out that grasscutters attacked farmlands in both dry and wet seasons but the attack became more intense in the wet season. This is quite understandable because farmers' planting season is usually synchronized with rainy season, more so that these are largely subsistence farmers. Small holder farmers can hardly afford irrigation farming system. Odebiyi and Alarape, (2018) took it further by relating this pattern of increased, crop raiding in wet season to period the primates in Kainji Lake National Park had less variety of fruits in the park.

The subsistence farmers adopted guarding and regular weeding as their strategies for preventing crop damage by wild animals, while they considered the regular weeding as the most effective, because there would not be hiding place for the problematic animals. Although several researchers have reported different preventive measures adopted by farmers and have equally made recommendations on the most effective approach. Most of these approaches centered on combination of two or more methods. As logical as it appears, there remains a missing link, which is the affordability of these preventive measures by peasant farmers who literally depend and survive on proceeds of their farming venture. This brings to bare the importance of government intervention. It was however disheartening, from the focal group discussion that there was no functional link between the farmers and relevant government agencies.

CONCLUSION

Crop raiding by wild pests is a menace among small holder farmers in Ayetoro, Ogun State, Nigeria. Maize, the farmers' staple food was the most frequently attacked crop. By implication, the farmers are prone to food insecurity and economic devastation.

Going forward, reports on wildlife pest should be presented in proper and more objective context. In other words, there should be a clear distinction between frequency of report and actual loss incurred by farmers. Undoubtedly, this is a tall order but it would facilitate a robust and highly objective policy formation on prevention and mitigation of human-wildlife conflicts. Issues on wildlife crop damage must be discussed and presented in proper context.

Wildlife pests raid in both season, and as such, mitigation measures should have a holistic approach in order to yield the desired results. There is an urgent need for government intervention in order to cushion the effect of the loss incurred by the farmers.

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